

PARKINSONS DISEASE DIAGNOSIS USING IMAGE PROCESSING TECHNIQUES A SURVEY

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ABSTRACT

Clinical Diagnosis of Parkinson's disease [PD] leads to errors, excessive medical costs, and provide insufficient services to the patients. There is no particular method or a test to detect the PD. The diagnosis of the Parkinson's disease needs an accurate detection. Computer Aided Diagnosis (CAD) gives accurate results to detect the PD. These CAD can be embedded into a real time application for the early diagnosis of PD. Dopamine nerve terminals can be reduced in the brain parts such as Substantia nigra, Striatum, and other brain structures. This reduction which will lead to Parkinson's disease. Dopamine Reduction gets automatically diagnosed by CAD and PD/normal patients can be found. For this, machine learning system (MLS)/CAD can be trained with the help of Artificial Neural Networks (ANN). Image processing techniques that are available to detect PD using MLS/CAD gets discussed in this paper.

Keywords

Parkinson's disease (PD), Statistical Parametric Mapping (SPM), Computer Aided Diagnosis (CAD)

1.INTRODUCTION

Parkinson's disease (PD), Statistical Parametric Mapping (SPM), Computer Aided Diagnosis (CAD)

Parkinson's disease is a second neurodegenerative disease which causes major threat to aged people and in the society as a whole and this is next to Alzheimer's disease [2]. Neurochemically, Parkinson's disease gets occurred due to the loss of dopamine nerve terminals in the region of striatum which are connects to the Substantia Nigra. Dopamine deficit may cause due to the loss of neurons in the midbrain of Substantia Nigra which will lead to the result that there occur changes within nigrostriatum neural conduction. Apart from that, PD can also characterize by the presence of intracytoplasmic inclusions called lewy bodies. Clinical diagnosis for each and every human may vary largely.

Problems with imbalance, tremor, postural instability, rigidity are all the major symptoms for PD. Motor symptoms usually start at one side of the body and gradually it will progress to the opposite side. Other parkinsonian syndromes are mainly affected by these symptoms. Idiopathic PD diagnosis indicators are symptoms, move to advanced stage, and treatment response based on levadopa. Tremor symptoms lead to loss of voluntary movement. Tremor may happen at thumb and wrist, which is one of the most typical initial symptoms. The amount of resistance can be measured by limb rigidity when it is moved passively. PD disease patients have higher resistance in limb than normal person. Changes in muscle and joints properties can also contribute to the presence of parkinsonian rigidity. Bradykinesia symptoms lead to some of the familiar problems such as difficult to sit and stand in a floor, get in and out of a car, chair. Bradykinesia symptoms

which are similar to akinesia and hypokinesia which also leads to loss of immobility. Postural instability may cause problems such as person suffer to sit independently, more disturbance in outside, doesn't stand individually, and inability to regain balance. An akinesia symptom leads to immovability of body movement, whereas range and size of movement gets decreased refers to hypokinesia. Problems with imbalance symptoms has not analyzed yet. It is very difficult to predict PD with the help of applicable environmental information.

Still there is no medical treatment to diagnose Parkinson's disease although medication is available while the symptoms are gets identified at early stages of this disease [3]. Early stage diagnosis can result in significant life saving. Parkinson's disease specialists make correct decisions by evaluating their test results of their patients. Diagnosing Parkinson's disease may need experience and highly skilled specialists [4]. Improvement of diagnosis and assessment in early disease can gets resolved by functional neuro imaging. Statistical Parametric Mapping (SPM) is a popular Matlab based software package for performing neuro imaging studies that can be used to locate significant effects of statistical parametric models in images. Biological Neural systems can be simulated by artificial neural Networks. There are number of nerve cells in human brain which are called as neurons where each neuron is connected to other neurons via stand of fiber called axons. Nerve impulses get transmitted from one neuron to other by axons, when the neurons are affected. Dendrites are the one which connects a neuron and axons of other neurons. The contact point between a dendrite and axon is called a synapse. The output of the network may be continuous or discrete. If it is discrete it performs prediction otherwise it performs classification. Detection of Normal/PD classes can be accepted even there is a small change in the arrangement of neurons and network. Most of the medical diagnosis uses classifier that will get increasing gradually. Advancements in artificial Intelligence led to the emergence of expert systems for medical applications. Classification systems can be used to improve accuracy, reliability of diagnosis and minimizing possible errors, as well as making the diagnoses of the disease more time efficient [4].

2.OVERVIEW OF ALGORITHM

Diagnosis and the detection of PD using automated image processing techniques at early stages are reviewed here is the main intension of this survey. In this paper, different methods based on machine learning techniques were mentioned for the diagnosis of PD. These processing algorithms provide more accuracy, sensitivity, specificity over the detection of the patients affected or not affected by PD.

2.1. DATASET

Multiple system atrophy, progressive supranuclear palsy is neurodegenerative disorder which is associated with PD. Visualization and assessment of changes in cerebral blood flow, glucose metabolism, and neurotransmitter can be done by Positron emission tomography (PET) and single-photon emission tomography (SPECT). Structural changes are very small and it can be diagnosed successfully at an early stage of this disease. Anatomical imaging modalities diagnostic accuracy (e.g., magnetic resonance imaging [MRI]) is not good in neurodegenerative disorder [5]. A change in neurotransmitter function gets noted particularly in the dopaminergic system which becomes evident long, before structural, metabolic or blood flow. Positron Emission tomography (PET) and single photon emission tomography (SPECT) images are preferred than MRI for the diagnosis of Parkinson's disease. PET and SPECT imaging uses the below two main paths:

1. To detect abnormal tissue functioning in neurons make a studies about blood flow and cerebral metabolism.

2. To study the loss of dopamine neurons keep monitor and track the imaging of dopaminergic neurotransmitter system.

2.2. PRE-PROCESSING

Image pre-processing is the technique which can be used to enhance data images prior to computational processing. Preprocessing an image which involves removing noise removal, normalization of intensity images, removing reflections, and masking portions of images.

Aprajita Sharma [6] presented the preprocessing techniques for MRI brain images. Dynamic speckle noise may arise from different tissues so that MRI images are very sensitive. These noises can be avoided by morphological operations. The main problem of reduction is that speckle is not a static noise but dynamic in image. Influence is not very considerable when a small image gets considered and their speckle noise can be reduced.

Jiri Blahuta, Tomas souk up [8] presents the techniques for preprocessing ultrasound images. Use diagnostic ultrasound for soft tissues. The main processing used here is Input images to be resized to 50x50 mm ROI with Substantia Nigra. All the input images are in gray scale. If input image is in 24 bit depth that is RGB, convert that RGB image into gray image using `rgb2gray` function. Therefore all the intensity value of that given image is in range (0; 255).

I.A. Illan, J.m Gorriz presented the normalization technique for preprocessing in SPECT images. Spatial normalization is one of the techniques similar to image registration. Human brain may differ in size and shape and they can be view in different view as sagittal, coronal and Hemispheric. The location of one subject's brain scan can correlated to the same location of another subject's brain scan is the main goal of spatial normalization. And also they used Intensity normalization. An intensity value in the brain gets normalized and it acts as a mean image. This value can be used as a feature for classifying the normal and Parkinson's disease affected person.

Dan Long, jinwei wang [23] performed data preprocessing by using Statistical Parametric Mapping (SPM8) probability maps. All the images were then resembled to an isotropic resolution of 3 mm at the end of the normalization and segmentation process can be applied across all of the subjects. Each of the every image gets modulated to the original image that is target image. Target image gets selected as a good quality image. The modulated image gets smoothed by a 10-mm full width at half maximum (FWHM) Gaussian kernel.

2.3. FEATURE EXTRACTION

The feature extraction [10] process can be used to reduce the input data dimension and minimize the training time taken by the classifier. From the Region of Interest (ROI) we can extract Geometrical, statistical, and texture moments [4]. These statistical features are extracted directly from the images. Statistical moments which include features such as mean value, Median Value, Standard Deviation, Skewness, Kurtosis. Gabor filters are employed to extract texture features. Gabor filters are very effective to extract these texture features.

Prashanth, Sumantra Dutta Roy [7], developed a machine learning algorithm for diagnosing Parkinson's disease. DaTSCAN SPECT images that are available from the PPMI database (<http://www.ppmi-info.org/about-ppmi/who-we-are/study-cores/>) were used to compute the striatal binding ratio (SBR) values of the four striatal regions (left and right caudate, left and right putamen). SBR Values contained in the database is calculated from 179 normal and 369 early PD subjects. Longitudinal subjects are evaluated in PPMI. Occital lobe region considered as the reference and using this, SBR values are calculated for the right caudate, left caudate, right putamen and left putamen.

Dan Long, jinwei wang [23] proposed that to test the hypothesis, first extract multi-level characteristics (ALFF, ReHo and RFCS) from the fMRI data and extract grey matter, white matter, and CSF volume from structural data. Intrinsic or spontaneous neural activity in the human brain gets indicated by ALFF. This is one of the effective indicators. In this paper ALFF can be calculated by voxel time series gets converted into the frequency domain using Fast Fourier Transform and from that power spectrum was obtained and then ALFF was calculated as the mean of this square root [24].The ALFF of each voxel was divided by the global mean value to reduce the global effects of variability in all subjects. ReHo features can be used to evaluate brain activities in the resting state by measuring the functional synchronization of a given voxel to its nearest neighbors. Average correlation of one region gets compared with all other regions which gets measured by RFCS.

2.4. FEATURE SELECTION

Principle Component Analysis is one of the feature selection techniques. The transformation of data space into a feature space is known as feature selection. This selection technique reduced number of effective features and retains only important intrinsic information data. A set of correlated variables gets converted into a new set of uncorrelated variables by using PCA. Aprajita Sharma [6] uses the PCA as a feature selection technique to reduce the dimensionality of the data.

Dan Long, jinwei wang [23] proposed that the feature selection method was used to compare the feature values of the various brain regions between the two subject groups. Two groups which have similar differences in features were selected.

XEL BASED MORPHOMETRY (VBM)

Thomas jubalt, Simons presented a voxel based morphometry technique. This is a neuroimaging analysis technique that allows investigation of focal differences in brain anatomy using statistical approach of SPM. This technique identifies local atrophies without the selection of region of interest. MRI images are used as an input image in this paper which includes two steps that is spatial preprocessing (normalization, segmentation, jacobian modulation and smoothing) and statistical analysis. These steps are implemented in SPM software package.

Figure1.Voxel Based Morphometry Steps

MRI images get preprocessed by one of the standard optimized procedure. [9]. Normalization process done by averaging all anatomical scans which produces template and priori images. First T1-weighted images were segmented and then processed. Normalized all grey/white matter

images to grey/white matter template. Original T1 images are then processed by white matter normalization parameters. At last Grey matter, White matter, and cerebrospinal fluid gets segmented from normalized images. To preserve initial volumes, jacobian determinants which gets derived from spatial normalization step were multiplied with grey matter, white matter voxel values to get an outcome of modulated white matter images.

12 mm FWHM isotropic Gaussian kernel can be used to spatially smooth modulated white matter images. False positive finding risk gets minimized by kernel size. Statistical testing may be performed on smoothed data using general linear model using covariance analysis, grey and white matter volume which is treated as nuisance covariates based on Gaussian theory. Loss of GM and WM volume reduction gets identified by statistical testing. False discovery rate correction at voxel level which are used to set statistical threshold at $p < 0.05$.

2.6.CLASSIFICATION

Classification step can be used to classify whether the patient affected by Parkinson's disease or not. The training and classification is done using Neural Network. Neural network technology offers a number of tools such as learning and adaption, generalization, robustness, feature extraction and distributed representation. Classification and recognition problem are gets easily solved by Artificial Neural Network.

Neuro fuzzy technology can be used for classification [6]. Neuro fuzzy technology can be constructed by using fuzzy operations at single neuron level. It includes both the advantages of both ANN and fuzzy logic. ANN requires large training set to achieve high accuracy. Fuzzy system more accurate but depends on expert knowledge.

Support Vector Machine(SVM) are supervised techniques for classification which finds a linear hyper plane by placing the largest margin by mapping input features to a higher dimensional space through either linear or nonlinear kernel functions. Prediction/Prognostic models gets developed that can be used to identify the purpose of risk prediction in PD with the help of multivariate logistic regression techniques. The probability occurrence of one out of two classes gets modeled by binomial logistic regression. Supervised learning algorithm which requires training data and one of the most powerful supervised classification algorithms is Support Vector Machine (SVM). The main intent of SVM classifier is to directly focus on finding classification boundary without probability estimation values. This classifier is also known as hard classifier. Moreover classification may be performed with the help of probability estimation and evaluate class-conditional probabilities are known as soft classifier [7].

Artificial Neural Network was used for classification. In this paper they create MLP topology with patternnet function with inputs, number of hidden layer and training function. Input is vectors with optimal position of ellipses for different images. Expected outcome may be a correct coordinates for ellipse. Learning position from different input images based on Substantia Nigra position is the main purpose of ANN [8]. With the help of that position new coordinates for the new image gets easily identified.

2.6.STATISTICAL PARAMETRIC MAPPING (SPM)

This is a method for processing and analysis of neuroimages. A MATLAB is a program for processing and analysis of functional neuroimages and molecular neuroimages. To locate valid changes in different subject scans neuro images with the help of SPM tool. It gets run in an MATLAB environment and freely downloadable. Spatial processing can be done by using affine transformation. Smoothing process can be done with the help of Gaussian kernel. With the help of masking, t test classifier can be used to diagnose PD from normal and PD patients. Statistical analysis can be carried out with the help of General Linear Model (GLM).

Figure2.Statistical Parametric Mapping (SPM) steps

4. RELATED WORK

Aprajita Sharma [6] presented that feature extraction and unsupervised clustering techniques are applied to MRI brain slices. Self organizing map (SOM) algorithm can be used for clustering which classify all the pixels to identified classes that identified classes are Normal or PD. Artificial neural network implements SOM that can be used to determine the main classes, where the number of classes can be unknown priori. Parkinson’s disease gets diagnosed in brain stem area with the help of Clustering technique.

Figure 3.Flow chart of Aparajita Sharma [6] Reference paper

Thomas Jubalt [9] contributes that Parkinson’s disease gets affected brain stem and this is the first identifiable stage along with this damage some of the other factors such as test report and other environmental information gets considered to improve earlier diagnosis of PD. Non motor symptoms get identified from this damage such as autonomic dysfunction and sleep disorders to proceed for further diagnosis. The **GOAL** of this paper is to characterize the volume reduction in white matter which are associated with PD. Steps of this paper are shown in Figure 2.

Jiri Blahuta [8] shows that medical ultrasound images get classified by using artificial intelligence with experimental software with MATLAB. Main **GOAL** of this paper is a classification of ROI substantia nigra in midbrain. Parkinson’s disease detection gets easily diagnosed from classified images. To measure the area of substantia nigra is one of the goals. The dimension of window with ROI was selected by neurologist. This paper future work will base on better accuracy for automatic positioning

Figure 4.Flow chart of whole processing of Jiri Blahuta [8]

R. Prashanth [7] proposed that recent neuroimaging techniques such as dopaminergic imaging use Single photon emission computed tomography (SPECT) are used to detect even early stages of this disease. Here use the striatal binding values (SBR) that are calculated from the PPMI database. This can be act as features which are passed to the classification step. SVM classification can be used to classify whether patient affected by Parkinson’s disease gets easily identified at an early stage.

The contributions of the present study are

- (1) High classification performance can be obtained using only four SBR feature without any feature selection techniques making the system simple.
- (2) Sample size used for this paper is very high.
- (3) High performance gets obtained.

Figure 5 Flow chart of whole processing of Prashanth [7]

Dan Long [23] proposed that diagnosis of Parkinson’s disease done by the integration of information from a variety of imaging modalities. Here they used the imaging modalities as resting state functional magnetic resonance imaging (rsfMRI). This paper deals with that which is the combination of both functional and structural imaging technology. They construct a non invasive multimodal magnetic resonance imaging algorithm framework for diagnosis of early PD. These systems which also can be used to distinguish between PD and Normal Group. Here they used template based approach to extract features and did not use region of interest (ROI) because ROI method is not suitable for the proper qualification of these changes.

Figure 6.Flow chart of whole processing of Dan Long [23]

I.A.Illan [28] proposed that computer aided diagnosis (CAD) system was designed to diagnose Parkinson’s disease at an early stage. Main aim of this work is to evaluate the SVM classification performance in DaTSCAN images, which gets compared to other possible classifiers. Processing involves in this tool are SPECT images are spatially normalized using the SPM8 software to performs that particular voxel in one position of one subject scan may corresponds to same voxel in another subject scan. This spatial Normalization technique based on affine transformation. After spatial normalization the second step is intensity normalization this can be used to establish comparisons between the areas of specific activity and the non specific activity. At last with the help of that normalization values that can be classified by three classification algorithms. 1. Support vector machines (SVM), 2. K-nearest neighbor, 3. Nearest mean. SVM classification provides best classification rates to near 90%. Some of the challenging task may be tackling by SVM.

Figure7.Flow chart of whole processing of Illan [23]

A Ram Yu [30] proposed that early diagnosis of Parkinson’s disease for rat brain. In this paper they used PET images. This will leads to good quality of the brain and it is one of the most important to visualize all of the brain structures in good quality. All of the processing is involved in SPM8 software. PET image having good quality was selected as a target image. Then all individual images were spatially normalized to the target image by using affine transformation. Extract the particular striatum position .To increase the signal to noise ratios Gaussian Kernel smoothing was used for smoothing purpose. Binding potential can be calculated in the second frame of PET data set by mean count of striatum minus mean count of cerebellum divided by mean count of cerebellum. To differentiate normal and PD classes two sample t-tests were performed by Binding potential calculation. Without the help of the SPM tool these techniques can be applied in MATLAB. They also extend to extract 2D shape and Volume Features.

Figure 8.Flow chart of whole processing of Ram Yu [30]

The Comparison of Performance, Advantages, Disadvantages of the above discussed papers has been organized and the detailed comparison table is shown below.

Paper Referred	Performance Measure	Advantages	Disadvantages
Ref Paper [6]	Accuracy of Diagnosis is Moderate.	NeuroFuzzy technique overcomes the drawback of ANN.	1. ANN require large training set to achieve high accuracy 2. Difficult to identify Abnormalities in MRI brain images.
Ref Paper [8]	Accuracy of Diagnosis is Approximately 70%.	ANN will be better trained for more input samples which lead to high accuracy.	Small number of training samples gets used.
Ref Paper [9]	Accuracy of diagnosis is moderate.	Registration and segmentation errors get avoided.	Brain stem nature gets vary due to registration.
Ref Paper [7]	SVM classifier produces Accuracy of more than 96%	1. Used four features without need of any feature selection technique. 2. High Performance.	Classification accuracy with logistic regression can be lower compared to SVM.

Ref Paper [23]	Diagnosis Yields good results with Accuracy=86.96%, sensitivity=78.95% Specificity=92.59%	1. Multiple Modalities can be used to extract more features. 2. Use template Based Approach to extract features not use ROI.	Small dataset samples can be used and this dataset may not applicable to other dataset.
Ref Paper [28]	Diagnosis Yields good results with Sensitivity=89.02% Specificity=93.21%	1. Remove Expensive manual operation. 2. Reduce time and cost.	Unavoidable errors gets occurred during Normalization
Ref Paper [30]	High Localization accuracy in diagnosis.	PET images shows a good quality of visualization of brain Structures.	Hard to perform the spatial Normalization using full frames data set. Easy to process in separate data set

5.CONCLUSION

Parkinson's disease caused by reduction of dopamine in nerve terminals and reduction cannot be diagnosed easily. Up to date there is no treatment, blood test to finding this disease. Over the past few years, neurology communities' researchers have received substantial attention for the recognition of substantia nigra, Striatum in brain stem. This attention may lead the researchers to working in diverse fields to detect PD. This survey paper proposed for automatic recognition of Striatum, substantia nigra in brain stem. PET imaging test can be used to detect reduction of dopamine in brain. Classification algorithms are used to distinguish between normal and PD. Therefore accurate diagnosis of PD and number of wrong decisions gets reduced with the help of CAD and diagnosis algorithms. Extracting features and selecting appropriate features will yields good classification results. To improve the overall performance of CAD and diagnosis algorithms, further developments in each algorithm step may require.

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